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Study of Environmental Justice in Agriculture and Food System in India

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Abstract:

As we know that, India is an agrarian country, most of its population depend upon agriculture for food and income, as it's the backbone of Nation as well as traditional business of most of the population of India. Global warming & climate changes forced policymakers to highlights the need & importance of environmental justice. Nowadays, each and every step taken by Indian Government, institution or any organization are aligned & towards to maintain the environmental justice. This is a conceptual paper and its aim is to introduce the concept of environmental justice and its importance in the agriculture and food system in India. In addition to this it also reviews the role of different agriculture and food system organisation and their contribution in environmental justice. It highlighted that marginal farmers have more potentials to take a production on large scale but they also facing the Socio-Economic challenges.

This paper concluded that with the help of environmental justice India can achieve the remarkable progress in sustainable development and can achieve the goal of government. The finding of this paper examine that the agriculture and food system institutes show the economic justice in subsidies, schemes, policy and trade practices. Also, food system keeps the nutritional value and deliver the quality food by maintaining social justice with food security.

Keywords: Social justice, Economic justice, Government, Agriculture, Marginal Farmers, Food System

Introduction:

As we all know that in old era environmental justice has a secondary concern in agriculture and food system practices. This paper is mainly focuses on economic and social justice. Agriculture is very fast-growing concept encompasses of number of allied activities. This paper cover the most of the aspect of economic justice which is depend upon resources availability, disparities in income sources, equitable distribution of incentives and subsidies, fair trade practices, fair wages, community empowerments, participatory approach in policy decision making and equal opportunities. Also Social justice ensure the purpose of food justice, community farming, health protection, food security and quality food. This paper mainly focus on Marginal farmers and the challenges faced by them to achieve environmental justice.

1. Objective of the Study:

- To study & understand the current status of socio-economic justice in agriculture and food system in India
- To study the role of NABARD, Agriculture Departments, and the APEDA that contribute towards the environmental justice in agriculture and food system.

- To understand the challenges faced by Marginal farmers to achieve economic and social justice.

2. Motivation of the Research:

1. Creating awareness about socio-economic justice in agriculture and food systems.
2. Motivating marginal farmers to achieve socio-economic justice for their well-being.
3. To wake up the farmers about role and contribution of agriculture department, NABARD and APEDA.

Literature Review

- Altieri (1995), in *Agroecology: The Science of Sustainable Agriculture*, advocates for agroecological practices that integrate traditional knowledge and promote environmental sustainability.
- Agricultural practices frequently amplify social inequities. Scholars such as Guthman (2011) highlight the disproportionate exposure of farmworkers—often low-income and minority populations—to pesticides and hazardous conditions. Furthermore, land tenure and resource allocation systems perpetuate systemic injustices (Pulido, 1996).
- Sustainable agriculture is posited as a solution to environmental degradation. Altieri (2009) emphasizes agroecological practices that integrate sustainability with equitable labor and land use practices. However, the implementation of such systems often fails to include the voices of marginalized stakeholders (Schlosberg, 2013).
- The concept of food sovereignty, as articulated by Patel (2007) in *Stuffed and Starved: The Hidden Battle for the World Food System*, emphasizes the right of people to healthy and culturally appropriate food produced through ecologically sound and sustainable methods. Patel explores how globalized food systems exacerbate inequalities, with local communities losing control over their agricultural resources.
- Alkon and Agyeman (2011), in *Cultivating Food Justice: Race, Class, and Sustainability*, examine grassroots movements advocating for equitable food access and community-led solutions
- Migrant labourers are among the most vulnerable populations in agriculture. Holmes (2013), in *Fresh Fruit, Broken Bodies: Migrant Farmworkers in the United States*, highlights the physical and psychological toll of exploitative labor practices. Bacon (2017), in *The Right to Stay Home: How US Policy Drives Mexican Migration*, connects these injustices to broader economic and political systems, emphasizing the need for fair labor

standards and immigration policies that support workers' rights.

- Marginalized communities often bear the brunt of environmental degradation caused by industrial agricultural practices. Shiva (2016), in *Earth Democracy: Justice, Sustainability, and Peace*, critiques the corporate dominance of global agriculture and its environmental.
- Effective policies addressing EJ in agriculture must integrate diverse perspectives, including those of indigenous communities and smallholder farmers (Whyte, 2018).
- The historical marginalization of minority and indigenous communities in agricultural systems is a recurring theme. White (2018), in *Freedom Farmers: Agricultural Resistance and the Black Freedom Movement*, documents how Black farmers were systematically excluded from federal programs such as the New Deal-era agricultural subsidies.
- Similarly, Mitchell and Chakrabarti (2021) analyse the long-term effects of discriminatory lending practices on land ownership among minority communities. These works underscore how historical policies perpetuate contemporary inequities in agricultural practices and land distribution.

Research Methodology

- **Research method-** In this research study exploratory method is used. To elaborate the concept as well as known facts are described related with topic.
- **Data collection method related with study-** this research study is based on secondary data

Secondary data: Websites- Ministry of agriculture, Institutions-APEDA, NABARD, Journals, Web pages-Internet surfing.

Types of research

Conceptual Research: Here ideas are interpreted and demonstrated by highlighting it in different way. Based upon the topic and known things.

4. The Current Status of Socio-Economic Justice in Agriculture and Food Systems in India.

In most of the rural area people are not aware about the concept of socio-economic justice that creates the existence of farmers and adding more value in their life to live happily and respectfully. In other words it's a battle for their right. It enlist that systematic inequalities such as disparities in wealth, power, access to resources, and opportunities perpetuate injustice and imbalance in the food system. Addressing these issues involves reshaping policies, practices, and relationships to foster equity and dignity for all participants in the agricultural and food sectors.

a. Key aspect of social justice:

- **Provide wellbeing facilities to migrant agricultural workforce:** for example In Maharashtra the education as well as quarter's facility are provided to the migrant agricultural workforce working in sugarcane factory. Also, in Nashik District of Maharashtra at the time of grape production the tribal workers are hired by grape producers on contract basis for particular period by providing them house, food security and well-being facility.
- **Involvement of Community:** Ensuring equal opportunity in placing their opinion and have a right indecision-making processes affecting agricultural and food systems.
- **Protecting the rights of migrant workers:** most of the agricultural workforce has to migrant from their own location in search of work. With the help of law particular protections are also given about their wages and right.
- **Avoid malnutrition due to food insecurity:** In rural area because of integrated intervention some of the marginal community facing this kind of problem.
- **Access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food:** Accessibility does not depend upon income, location or position of a people.
- **Implementing safety measures:** Implementing safety measures to protect the workers. Without considering religion, gender or any other basis to judge him or her. Safety is the first concern in agriculture and food system.
- **Education and Awareness:** Building consumer consciousness about ethical food consumption and sustainable practices.

Other than this there are many key aspects about social justice in agriculture and food system the main motive behind this is to avoid any kind of discrimination base upon gender, religion, income or any other factor..

b. Key aspect of Income justice :

- **Support for marginal Farmers:** Providing financial and technical support to marginal farmers because they suffer more as compare to large holding farmers. With a view to improve the condition of Small and Marginal farmers and double the income of farmers by 2022, Government is realigning its interventions from production-centric approach to farmers' income-centric initiatives, with focus on better and new technological solutions.
- **Avoid middleman intermediary:** due to interference of middleman the farmer does not get the right price to their produce because of this there is income disparities. Also, it creates

barriers to food system to reach towards the consumer within a period.

- **Supporting ethical food system:** implements proper regulatory channels to avoid malpractices for example using harmful chemicals in agriculture produce to increase the profit etc. in food system
- **Employment opportunities in agriculture:** Provide income sources in agriculture and allied activity. Implement agriculture skill development program and Agri-business opportunities to generate income.
- **Local Food Systems:** Supporting local and urban farming initiatives to empower communities and reduce environmental impacts.
- **Equitable Subsidies:** Addressing disparities in how agricultural subsidies are distributed, often favouring large-scale industrial farms.
- **Implementing Government schemes:** National Agriculture Market scheme (e-NAM), National Food Security Mission (NFSM) to achieve the social and economic justice.
- **Create scope for agriculture export:** strengthen the international trade practices to build the economy.

5. Role of (Nabard), Agriculture Departments, and the (Apeda) That Contributes Towards the Environmental Justice in Agriculture and Food Systems.

Institutions like the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD), Agriculture Departments, and the Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority (APEEDA) play the crucial roles in promoting socio-economic justice in agriculture and food systems by addressing inequalities, empowering farmers, and fostering sustainability

1. National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD)

Key Contributions:

- **Financial Inclusion and Support for Marginalized Farmers:** NABARD provides financial assistance to small and marginal farmers through rural banks, cooperative societies, and microfinance institutions.

It offers loans and refinancing for agricultural and rural development projects, ensuring accessibility to credit for disadvantaged communities.

- **Infrastructure Development:** The institution finances the development of rural infrastructure like irrigation systems, storage facilities, cold chains, and rural roads, which improve market access and reduce post-harvest losses.
- **Sustainable Agriculture:** NABARD promotes eco-friendly farming practices such

as organic farming, water conservation, and watershed management through programs like the Watershed Development Fund .It supports climate-resilient agriculture to address the impacts of climate change on vulnerable farmers.

- **Skill Development and Capacity Building:** NABARD conducts training programs to enhance farmers' skills in modern farming practices, market linkages, and financial literacy. It supports rural entrepreneurship by funding self-help groups (SHGs) and farmer producer organizations (FPOs).
- **Livelihood Support:**The bank promotes rural non-farm sector activities to diversify incomes and reduce dependency on agriculture, ensuring socio-economic stability.

Impact on Socio-Economic Justice: NABARD plays a significant role in reducing rural poverty and income inequality by empowering marginal farmers and landless workers. Its focus on gender inclusion supports to women farmers and entrepreneurs, fostering equity.

2. (Agriculture Department State and National Level)

Key Contributions:

- **Policy Formulation and Implementation:** The Agriculture Departments at the state and national levels develop and implement policies to ensure food security, enhance agricultural productivity, and support marginalized farmers.
- **Subsidies and Schemes for Farmers:** Provide subsidies on seeds, fertilizers, irrigation, and farm machinery to reduce the input costs for small and marginal farmers. Implement welfare schemes like the **PM-KISAN** scheme in India, which offers direct income support to farmers.
- **Support for Sustainable Farming:** Promote sustainable agricultural practices through organic farming initiatives, soil health programs, and integrated pest management. Drive the adoption of technologies like precision farming, which reduces resource wastage.
- **Market Linkages:** Facilitate market access through programs like e-NAM (National Agriculture Market) in India, which connects farmers with buyers, ensuring fair prices for their produce. Organize agricultural fairs and exhibitions to provide platforms for farmers to showcase and sell their products.
- **Disaster Management and Relief:** Provide timely assistance to farmers affected by droughts, floods, and other natural disasters through compensation and crop insurance schemes.

- **Capacity Building:** Train farmers in advanced agricultural techniques and provide extension services to ensure knowledge dissemination.

Impact on Socio-Economic Justice: By ensuring equitable access to resources, subsidies, and support, Agriculture Departments reduce income disparities and protect the rights of smallholder farmers.They play a vital role in addressing rural unemployment and ensuring food security for all sections of society.

3. Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority (APEDA)

Key Contributions:

- **Promoting Agricultural Exports:** APEDA works to enhance the export potential of Indian agricultural and processed food products, creating opportunities for farmers and food producers to access international markets.
- **Infrastructure Development:** Develops export infrastructure, such as pack houses, cold storages, and food processing units, ensuring quality compliance and reducing post-harvest losses.
- **Certification and Standards:** Implements stringent quality standards and certifications (like organic certification) to ensure that Indian agricultural products meet global market requirements.
- **Market Intelligence and Training:** Provides farmers and exporters with market insights, training, and technical assistance to improve product quality and competitiveness in global markets.
- **Support for Value Addition:** Encourages value addition in agricultural products, such as processing fruits into juices or spices into packaged goods, increasing the income of farmers and rural entrepreneurs.
- **Focus on Niche and Organic Products:** Promotes organic farming and exports, ensuring premium pricing for eco-friendly products and supporting sustainable agricultural practices.

Impact on Socio-Economic Justice: APEDA helps small and marginal farmers integrate into global value chains, ensuring better income and reducing poverty. By promoting sustainable practices and organic farming, it addresses environmental concerns while improving farmer livelihoods. Encourages rural entrepreneurship and employment through value addition and export-oriented farming.

Collaborative Impact on Agriculture and Food Systems

- **Equity in Resource Distribution:** Institutions like NABARD ensure financial equity by extending credit to disadvantaged farmers, while Agriculture Departments provide

subsidies and support. APEDA's focus on export opportunities helps marginalized farmers access global markets.

- **Sustainability and Environmental Justice:** All three institutions promote sustainable farming practices, addressing the environmental impacts of agriculture and ensuring long-term resilience.
- **Food Security and Poverty Alleviation:** These institutions contribute to food security by enhancing productivity, reducing wastage, and improving market access, lifting millions out of poverty.
- **Empowerment of Marginalized Groups:** Specific programs target women, smallholders, and tribal communities, ensuring their inclusion in the agricultural economy.
- **Employment Generation:** Infrastructure development, value addition, and export promotion create jobs in rural areas, reducing migration and improving rural livelihoods.

Examples of Successful Initiatives

- **NABARD's SHG-Bank Linkage Program:** Empowered millions of rural women by linking self-help groups to formal banking.
- **PM-KISAN Scheme:** Direct income transfer to farmers ensured socio-economic stability.
- **APEDA's Promotion of Mango Exports:** Provided opportunities for smallholder mango farmers to access premium markets like Europe.

6. Challenges Faced By Marginal Farmers to Achieve Socio-Economic Justice.

Marginal farmers, defined as those owning less than 1-2 hectares of land, face numerous challenges in achieving economic and social justice. These challenges can be broadly categorized into economic, social, environmental, and institutional dimensions

1. Economic Challenges

- **Limited Landholdings:** Small land sizes reduce economies of scale, limiting productivity and profitability.
- **Low Productivity:** Marginal farmers often lack access to quality seeds, fertilizers, and irrigation facilities, leading to suboptimal yields.
- **Financial Constraints:** Poor access to credit and high dependency on informal moneylenders with exorbitant interest rates exacerbate their economic vulnerability.
- **Market Access:** Marginal farmers face difficulties in accessing markets, fair prices, and value chains due to inadequate infrastructure and exploitation by intermediaries.
- **Lack of Diversification:** Dependence on subsistence farming makes them highly

vulnerable to price fluctuations and crop failures.

2. Social Challenges

- **Social Inequities:** Marginal farmers often belong to socially disadvantaged groups such as Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, or other marginalized communities, compounding their struggles.
- **Lack of Education:** Limited literacy and education restrict their ability to adopt modern farming techniques or engage in alternative livelihoods.
- **Gender Inequality:** Women farmers, often involved in unpaid agricultural labor, face systemic discrimination and lack of recognition as landowners or primary producers.
- **Health and Nutrition:** Poverty leads to poor living conditions, inadequate healthcare, and malnutrition among marginal farming households.

Findings

- With the help of socio-economic justice India can achieve the remarkable progress in sustainable development and food security.
- It helps the small farmers to improve their standard of living
- Government taking the initiative to implement the different scheme to generate the income and opportunities and also strengthen the food system.
- In India, it is observed that there are many organisations that promote agricultural export activity and achieve the economic justice in international market
- It also contributes towards the community development programmes.
- Farmers are more aware about the agricultural subsidies and scheme for economic development.

Conclusions

Socio economic justice is very vast concept. Now, farmers are aware about it and take the action for their right which leads their social well-being and economic conditions. Also, it has a multidisciplinary approach that cover each and every activity related with agriculture and food system. By implementing Ethical activity quality of agriculture produce is enhance which ultimately satisfy the goal of government that is food security. the role of different organisation like Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority (APEDA) play the crucial role in promoting agricultural export and processed food to capture global market. The marginal farmers also have intense potential to increase their production by doing export oriented farming their many institutions that provide financial and technical

assistance to improve the social as well as economic development of marginal farmers.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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